

Relaying Schemes and Rate-distance trade-off for Multihop QKD

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Abstract—In recent years, quantum communications have garnered considerable attention for their potential to enhance network security. Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) protocols, which promise theoretically secure key generation for remote nodes, have been a primary focus. However, QKD faces significant challenges due to its limited range, especially for fiber-based channels, until quantum repeaters are technologically feasible. Consequently, research efforts have been redirected towards secure communication via QKD nodes within multi-hop networks, as a first step towards realizing the quantum internet. In this paper, we propose and analyze a key relay protocol (KRP) for secure quantum key generation within a three-node network, which can be extended to more than two hops in a straightforward manner. We analyzed security under two different sets of assumptions at each node plus accurately evaluated the achievable key rate via numerical methods. Finally, we discuss the advantages and limitations of the proposed protocol.

Index Terms—Quantum key distribution, One time pad, Numerical simulation, Key rate

I. INTRODUCTION

Quantum computation has revolutionized the field of secure communications. It is expected that in next years quantum computers will threaten almost all known communications [1], and intense research effort is being focused on two main potential solutions: replacing current cryptography with stronger Post quantum algorithms [2] (PQC), and Quantum Communications (QC), which aims to improve transmission security by exploiting the laws of physical quantum systems. We study in this work a simple QKD network, namely a two-hop chain of QKD nodes, in order to increase the effective distance of quantum communications, which is severely limited in practice by photon attenuation in fiber-based channels up to a maximum around 100 km [3], [4]. A major challenge to spread the use of QKD is to devise solutions for establishing secure communications through untrusted third-party nodes in a multi-hop series of links, since this is a key problem toward the realization of the Quantum Internet. However, to date,

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achieving information-theoretically secure long-range QKD communications under the assumption of untrusted nodes remains an open problem [5].

In this paper, we propose a protocol that facilitates the realization of key generation between two QKD end nodes connected through a third intermediate node with relaxed assumptions on the security and control of this relay node. We provide the specification of the key generation protocol, the actions at the relay node, and the security guarantees of the scheme, which depends on the available resources available at each one of the three nodes. The protocol can be extended, with minor modification, to longer linear topologies. OpenQKDSecurity [6] is used to numerically evaluate two different quantum communication channels, in three different configurations: short-range networks ($d \approx 1$ km), mid-range networks (e.g., metropolitan, $d = 20$ km) and long-distance networks.

The paper is organized as follows. In Section II, we briefly review related work. Section III summarizes the theoretical background on QKD, and next in Section IV we describe the proposed multi-hop QKD protocol along with its security analysis. We used a numerical simulation tool (Section V) to obtain the numerical results shown and discussed in Section VI. Finally, in Section VII the main conclusions are drawn.

II. RELATED WORK

Due to the distance limitation that QKD presents, the approach of combining the QKD protocol with the OTP arises as a natural solution [7]. The technique proposed in [8] for communication between two nodes combines QKD, OTP and Huffman encryption. With the use of a trusted node, the protocol is divided in three steps: First, the QKD protocol. Next, the information is sent and the OTP and encoding are applied. Finally, the information is decrypted and received by the end node. The technique proposed in [9] is a three-party authentication protocol based on a time-bound criterion, where the trusted node generates the time bound for the clients and the clients generate their keys themselves. It consists of two phases: a communication phase where the parties obtain their time bound from the trusted center, followed by trusted communications to generate and distribute their keys. Key generation is performed in a second phase. For more than three

users, [10] uses a multicast router in charge of distributing and managing the keys created by QKD. The protocol consists of three phases: keys generation by QKD; authentication, making sure that no one except the legitimate user receives the message and making sure that nobody except the legitimate sender writes or modifies it; data encryption with the secure key and transmission to receivers.

Other works integrate the use of Quantum OTP with classical digital signature technologies to amplify the security and make the global procedure more robust [11], [12]. There have also been successful deployments of quantum OTP networks, as in [13], demonstrating a secure video conference over the Tokyo QKD network based on a QKD-OTP key relaying protocol, at an encryption rate of 128 kbps. In this testbed, the keys were stored and distributed by a Key Management Agent located at every node. Another more recent example is [14], where an architecture is proposed for a four-node network. This work leverages a SDN-based control plane to implement a flexible Key Management System (KMS). Also, the work in [15] deals with the problem of routing for QKD networks,

III. QUANTUM KEY DISTRIBUTION

To achieve perfectly secure communications, we have to resort to Quantum Communications, whose security is rooted on the laws of physics, in the properties of quantum bits (qubits) rather than in mathematical and computational hardness assumptions. A qubit is any physical object that behaves as a quantum system with two orthogonal states which can be measured and reliably converted to a classical bit of information. Polarization of single photons (vertical \uparrow and horizontal \rightarrow) or particles with spin $\pm 1/2$ are examples of physical realization of a qubit.

As physical quantum entities, qubits can be in any superposition of the orthogonal basis states, e.g., the states

$$\begin{aligned} |\nearrow\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow\rangle + |\rightarrow\rangle) \\ |\nwarrow\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow\rangle - |\rightarrow\rangle). \end{aligned}$$

represent diagonally polarized photons that are a 50%/50% combination of a horizontally and a vertically polarized photon. A stream of $|\nearrow\rangle$ photons polarized will be detected after a \uparrow polarizer (resp., a \downarrow polarizer) with 50% probability. The measurement makes the quantum state to collapse to one of the two possible outcomes, and can be used to check security. In quantum-based communications, information theoretical security security arises as a consequence of the no-cloning theorem: the fact that it is impossible to create copy of an unknown arbitrary quantum state. So, if an eavesdropper attempts to intercept or copy the qubits used for transmission, the qubits will be altered and this change can be detected by the receiver.

QKD protocols take advantage of this for generating a common secret key between two parties over an open quantum channel (QC) with the assistance of a classical channel (CC). BB84 [16], one of the first and practically more important QKD protocols, works as follows:

- 1) Preparation: The sender prepares qubits in 4 different states: 0° (\rightarrow) and 90° (\uparrow) polarization, the Z basis; and 45° (\nearrow) and 135° (\nwarrow) polarization, the X basis. The sender chooses randomly between these states and keeps track of every basis that has been chosen while sending the qubits.
- 2) Measurement: The receiver measures the qubits with the X or the Z basis, at random, and keeps track of the basis used.
- 3) Key extraction: The sender and receiver share the bases used and the positions of undetected qubits via a non-protected CC, and keep the measured bits corresponding to the bases that match. These bits will be used to derive the sifted key, k . The positions of the undetected qubits will be used to form the raw key k_r , which correspond to the whole sequence of bits that made it to the receiver.

Now, if the QC is compromised, the receiver would detect, after knowing the sender's bases selection, the presence of the eavesdropper, since the fraction of matched bases used for the qubits would deviate significantly from the expected 75%.

BB84 falls in the category of the so-called prepare and measure protocols, because the security of the process is guaranteed by the process of measurement. A different class of QKD protocols inherit their security from entanglement of photons, like MDIBB84 [17], wherein a stream of pairs of entangled photons is sent to both end nodes, measured thereafter at the receiving nodes, and the secret key is obtained with a similar exchange of the measurement outcomes on an open CC.

IV. QKD PROTOCOLS AND MULTIPLE HOPS

While theoretically secure, QKD protocols are highly sensitive to decoherence and loss of photons, i.e., to the distance of the communications link. Depending on the technology and class, the achievable key rate drops drastically beyond a given threshold (≈ 100 km for BB84 with current technology). Thus, long-distance secure key agreement with QKD is in practice strongly limited by the link length, and for overcoming this limit splitting the total length with the insertion of intermediate relays is the only solution. Since quantum repeaters are still an immature and complex technology, a QKD relay able to forward the secret data generated on adjacent QKD links is necessary.

In order to preserve the information-theoretical security (ITS) provided by QKD, a QKD relay works just as two independent QKD endpoints which generate secret keys both with its downstream and upstream nodes, A and B . A common, perfectly secure secret key between A and B can be generated then by merging both keys as in a classical one-time-pad scheme (OTP) [18]. OTP guarantees ITS provided the bits being merged are uniformly random, the length of the OTP is equal or greater than the message length, and the OTP is unknown to any third party. Thus, ideally, QKD relays must be fully trusted devices, meaning that they are cryptographically secure and controlled by a trusted entity. Relaxing the trusted assumption is desirable but complex [19],

Fig. 1. (Color online) Schematic representation of the protocol described in IV-A. The steps of the protocol where information is sent are described by its order in the protocol and what they transmit. Blue color means transmission through QC and dark magenta through CC.

Fig. 2. (Color online) Schematic representation of the protocol described in IV-A. The steps of the protocol are described by its order in the protocol.

even partially. Dynamic KMS have been suggested as a technique for overcoming strong trust [14], [20].

In this Section, we describe two variations on KRP for multi-hop QKD which facilitate the relaxation of trust conditions on the QKD relays. While generic, for the sake of simplicity we will describe the protocols for two hops only, the extension to more hops is immediate.

As explained in Section III, there exist asymmetric and symmetric QKD protocols with respect to the location of the quantum source (e.g., BB84 and MDI). Thus, there are two possible scenarios to consider: both end nodes are quantum emitters and send qubits to the middle node (Fig. 1), or the middle node sends qubits to the end nodes (Fig. 3).

A. Asymmetric QKD protocol

In this scheme, the two end nodes, Alice and Bob, are equipped with a SPS (Single-photon Source), and the QKD relay is equipped with an SPD (Single-Photon Detector)¹ (Fig. 1). The steps of the proposed protocol are as follows:

¹It is possible to have different detectors for each of the channels, but realistically this will never be implemented and only one detector will be used for both of the signals, as the SPDs are generally the most expensive piece of equipment.

- 1) Alice and Bob will be permanently running a BB84 protocol with the QKD relay, continuously generating keys. The time τ to generate the keys will be limited by the key rate of the worst QC, of order $\tau \propto 1/K$.
- 2) Whenever the relay gets k_a and k_b , it forms the shared key k_s .
- 3) The relay sends the shared key k_s to Alice and Bob via CC.
- 4) Both Alice and Bob can use their own sifted key to extract the other key, as $k_s \oplus k_a = (k_a \oplus k_b) \oplus k_a = k_b$ and $k_s \oplus k_b = (k_a \oplus k_b) \oplus k_b = k_a$.
- 5) Now Alice and Bob share two quantum generated keys, which can be used as a OTP.

Fig. 2 depicts a schematic temporal representation of the protocol. The two keys of length L will complement a message of length M to form a message with ITS. The determination of the initial key to be employed for message encoding will be determined by the chronological order of their creation, and this information can be incorporated as a header during the transmission of the key k_s in the third step.

Nevertheless, this protocol cannot be implemented with an untrusted QKD relay, as all of the keys used in OTP are simultaneously available in the relay node at some point in time. Note, however, the security on the CC is not critical, since as long as the QC is secure, an eavesdropper with full access to all CCs will always have to guess a key of L randomly generated bits in order to get M bits of the message, so the only information gain is the length L of the key.

B. Symmetric QKD protocol

Assume now that the end nodes are equipped with SPDs and the QKD relay has a SPS, as represented in Fig. 3. In this case, we could devise a protocol analogous to the previous one, with the only difference being the asymmetry of the BB84 protocol. But we can take advantage of that asymmetry, and force the key agreement to be made in the end nodes only, to yield a more robust protocol, which could be implemented regardless of the level of trust assigned to the QKD relay. The logic behind this approach lies in the prevention of simultaneous coexistence of both keys, k_a and k_b , in the relay node. We will assume that the QKD relay sends the same qubits through both the channels. Then, the protocol is as follows:

- 1) Alice and Bob run continuously a BB84 protocol with the relay node, generating a stream of keys. The time τ to generate the keys will be limited by the key rate of the worst QC, of order $\tau \propto 1/K$.
- 2) Whenever the middle node registers the achievement of L bits from both channels ($L' = 2L/K$ qubits sent), it notifies to both of the end nodes, disclosing which node got it first.
- 3) The end nodes will send the positions of the wrong bases from the QKD protocol directly to the other node.
- 4) The end nodes can use these wrong basis positions plus their own to convert the received bits to the shared key k_s ($k_a = k_b = k_s$) by subtracting the spare bits that

Fig. 3. (Color online) Schematic representation of the protocol described in IV-B. The steps of the protocol where information is sent are described by its order in the protocol and what they transmit.

Fig. 4. (Color online) Schematic temporal representation of the protocol described in IV-A. The steps of the protocol are described by its order in the protocol. Blue color means transmission through QC and dark magenta through CC.

are in the wrong positions cooperatively with the other node.

- 5) Finally, Alice and Bob share a quantum generated key without direct quantum communication between them, which can be used as a OTP.

See Fig. 4 for a schematic temporal representation of the protocol.

In this scheme, the relay node does not have the information of the OTP keys, so as long as the QCs are secure, this protocol will be secure and the OTP will guarantee ITS.

C. Security - Key rate concession

There are instances where achieving the maximum possible key rate is more important than having ITS security. E.g., in the case where the security of the CCs accompanying the QCs is guaranteed, the generated bit sequence k_R can be sent through the CCs, and the final length of k_s will be (statistically) doubled, because the end nodes can then apply the other's node incorrect bases to extract k_a and k_b from k_R . This process increases the length of the OTP key by a factor

of 4, but the security of the process is heavily compromised, since access to the classical channel between relay and end nodes would automatically give away the OTP key.

Another concession can be done by pre-sharing a basis selection algorithm between end nodes, and the protocol ends in step 2, which is marginally faster. As previously seen, omitting a pure random basis selector breaks one of the ITS requisites, although still cryptographically secure.

We will compare these protocols numerically to show how much of an improvement in the key rate one can obtain given the trade-off in security.

An analysis of the security of the QC is out of the scope of this paper, but more sophisticated adversary models can be introduced [21], [22].

V. NUMERICAL CALCULATION OF THE KEY RATE

We have tested our multi-hop proposal by adapting the OpenQKDSecurity [6] numerical simulator, in which the key rate is estimated by convex optimization (module CVX). Since OpenQKDSecurity supports only a single point-to-point link, a new configuration module was added to establish the parameters of real channels and to fix a given key rate to generate the OTP. The configurable parameter for each link (in csv format, `inputfile.csv`) include the attenuation η (dB/km) suffered by the qubits in the QC; the distance D (km) of the QC; the qubit generation rate Q (Hz); the misalignment SPE (rad) for emitter and receiver; the dark count probability DC for successful measurement; the detector efficiency DE ; the error correction efficiency ECI (this number is > 1); the total number of qubits sent N ; and Nominal Capacity C (kbps) of the classical channel.

A. Key rate

Calculating the key rate in a given quantum link requires the computation of quantum entropies with the particular measurement operators involved in the protocol operations. Generally, this task is formulated as a semi-definite optimization program (SDP), for which there exist in some cases efficient numerical solvers. Formally, the key rate is the solution to the problem

$$K' = \left(\min_{\rho \in D} S(\rho) \right) - p_{\text{pass}} \cdot \text{leak}_{\text{obs}}^{\text{EC}}. \quad (1)$$

where K' is the probability of obtaining a usable bit per qubit sent. The actual key rate K is obtained by multiplying K' by the qubit generation rate Q . The first term $f(\rho)$ is the quantum relative entropy, $S(\rho) := -\text{Tr}(\rho \log \rho)$, minimized for all eavesdropping attacks provided that they are congruent with real observables and their expected values. As $S(\rho)$ is concave in ρ and D is convex as well, this is a tractable convex optimization problem, for which standard numerical solvers exist [23]. The second term $p_{\text{pass}} \cdot \text{leak}_{\text{obs}}^{\text{EC}}$ accounts for the probability of passing post selection times the number of publicly revealed bits during error correction (per post selected signal). OpenQKDSim tackles this problem with a two-step solution: (1) finding a worst-case eavesdropping attack (this gives upper bound for the key rate); and (2) mapping the upper bound to a lower bound.

TABLE I

KEY RATES FOR EACH OF THE DIFFERENT CONFIGURATIONS OF THE SYSTEM. THE KEY RATE IS ALWAYS LIMITED BY THE WORST CHANNEL OF THE TWO.

Distance $D_a - D_b$ (km)	K (Hz)
1 - 1	4586.68
1 - 20	1899.75
1 - 60	283.74
20 - 20	1899.75
20 - 60	283.74
60 - 60	283.74

It is proven in [23] that (1) is an upper bound to

$$\beta(\sigma) := f(\sigma) - \text{Tr}(\sigma^T \nabla f(\sigma)) + \max_{\vec{y} \in D^*} \vec{\gamma} \cdot \vec{y}, \quad (2)$$

where $D^* := \{\vec{y} \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid \sum_i y_i \Gamma_i^T \leq \nabla f(\sigma)\}$, Γ_i are the Hermitian operators such that $\text{Tr}(\Gamma_i \rho) = \gamma_i$, for all i , and γ_i are the expected values of the operators. Although [23] assumes the asymptotic limit, for our numerical results we will use the finite key solver to get more accuracy. The calculations for the finite-length regime can be found in [24].

B. OTP

OTP will impact on the actual key rate of the proposed multi-hop scenarios. To estimate that impact, the time to extract bits from the qubits and the delay of the CCs should be considered. This extra OTP waiting time is determined by (1) the quantum key generation time, approximately, the inverse of the key rate; and (2) the delay in the CCs, considering the times information goes through that channels; (3) and the delay due to channel's capacity delay, i.e. bits per second supported by the channel. If the processing time of qubits is considered invariant (and from now on, neglected), the generation time τ for a key to be generated is:

$$\tau = \frac{2L}{\min(K_a, K_b)} + \frac{S \cdot \max(D_a, D_b)}{c} + \frac{nL}{\min(C_a, C_b)}, \quad (3)$$

where S is the number of times information goes through the CC in the protocol, D_i are the distances of each channel, c is the propagation speed of the information, n is the factor that L bites of information are sent through the CC and C_i are the transmission rates of the CCs.

VI. RESULTS

Throughout this paper, we have treated BB84 independently of the rest of the protocol. This approach is motivated by the fact that the simulator evaluates the BB84 protocol collectively, and only provides the key rate as the output, disregarding the asymmetry of the process. The byproduct of this is the complete equivalence of the two possible protocols discussed. For this reason, we will compare only the three protocol variants discussed in IV-B, given that the results for the original protocol encompass both systems. The results, K and τ , for all different distance permutations are presented in Table I and Table II.

We used in (3) the values $L = 2048$ bits, $S = n = 3$, $c = 3 \cdot 10^5$ km/s; for the physical channels, we set $\eta = 0.2$ dB/km, $Q = 0.1$ MHz, $ECI = 1.16$ for both links, and $SPE = 0.05$,

Fig. 5. (Color online) Key rate for varying length of secondary channel while primary channel length is fixed. Plateaus indicate that varying the distance in that range does not worsen/improve the final key rate.

$DE = 0.6$, $C = 1$ Gbps for Alice's channel and $SPE = 0.12$, $DE = 0.5$, $C = 0.1$ Gbps for Bob's channel.

According to Table I, we can conclude that there is one channel that does not play a critical role in the process, as the worst channel will always be limiting the key rate. Fig. 5 plots the maximum distance until which Alice's channel can be extended if Bob's channel is fixed, in our case around ~ 14 km for the three configurations. This means that, using classical protocols, one is always limited by the worse quantum channel involved.

Our numerical results also indicate that the usage of a pre-shared basis selection algorithm produces approximately twice the key rate as originally (Table II), however only marginally faster than the Secure relay CC protocol, because the key agreement that comes after each node has generated its own key through the CC is avoided. The contribution from the QKD process is orders of magnitude greater. For that reason, when there exists a basis selection algorithm, the time is nearly halved. And similarly, when they raw key from the relay can be accessed by the end nodes, the necessary qubits to achieve the same key is halved, and two keys per round are generated, so the time per key is 4 times faster.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

We have reviewed the theory behind the BB84 protocol and the OTP technique, and used it to build a protocol based on a three node system incorporating both technologies, and evaluated its performance. Simulation results show that with classical protocols, QKD without direct quantum communication between two nodes can be achieved, but the worse channel key rate is always the limiting factor. In this contribution, ideal assumptions about the CCs and the information that goes through them have been taken. As future work, an actual simulation of the process of OTP creation will be carried out. Another question is whether or not we can expand to more

TABLE II
WAITING TIMES FOR EACH OF THE DIFFERENT CONFIGURATIONS OF THE SYSTEM. THE WORST CHANNEL OF THE TWO ALWAYS ESTABLISHES THE WAITING TIME.

Distance $D_a - D_b$ (km)	τ (s)		
	Original protocol	Secure relay CC	Pre-shared algorithm
1 – 1	1.78606	0.89304	0.89302
1 – 20	4.31214	2.15628	2.15607
1 – 60	28.87113	14.43617	14.43556
20 – 20	4.31214	2.15628	2.15607
20 – 60	28.87113	14.43617	14.43556
60 – 60	28.87113	14.43617	14.43556

than 2 hops and more complex networks and how to properly adapt the protocols. In this scenario, the design of a protocol to distribute the OTP is an ongoing work, the most plausible solution will involve a dynamic KMS.

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